

NUTRITIONAL AND SENSORY ASSESSMENT OF FRESH AND OSMOTICALLY DEHYDRATED CHAYOTE (*SECHIAM EDULE*) IN JUICE APPLICATIONS

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Abstract: As vegetables and fruits come under perishable commodities, preserving them for longer time for their usage is essential. One of the best techniques to preserve these is Dehydration. One such way of dehydration through osmosis is called Osmotic Dehydration. Chayote is one such underexplored vegetable that has great therapeutical and nutritional potential. The present study was carried out to analyse nutritional and mineral profile of fresh and osmotically dehydrated chayote vegetable. Proximate analysis was done for (Moisture, Protein, Fat, Fibre, Ash and Carbohydrate). Mineral analysis was done for (Iron, Calcium, Potassium, Sodium, Phosphorous and Iodine). The nutrients estimated were found to be Moisture (35.8 ± 0.12 to 67.2 ± 0.77), Protein (1.16 ± 0.04 to 5.52 ± 0.27), Fat (0.3 ± 0.1 to 0.8 ± 0.1), Fibre (1.38 ± 0.02 to 7.73 ± 0.17), Ash (2.63 ± 0.2 to 7.73 ± 0.17) and Carbohydrate (11.7 ± 0.17 to 57.3 ± 0.08). Minerals estimated were found to be Iron (2.29 ± 0.14 to 2.28 ± 0.01), Calcium (3.22 ± 0.08 to 6.4 ± 0.27), Potassium (7.66 ± 0.27 to 10.21 ± 0.1), Sodium (24.66 ± 1.24 to 86.3 ± 1.24), Phosphorous (2.42 ± 0.1 to 5.58 ± 0.27) and Iodine (4.23 ± 0.04 to 7.46 ± 0.17). The sensory analysis of developed juices determined that all the products were overall acceptable by the consumers. Overall, osmotic dehydration significantly retained nutrients due to mild conditions, whereas these were not retained by conventional drying technique due to prolonged exposure to heat and temperature.

Key words: Vegetable, Osmotic dehydration, Chayote, Therapeutical, Nutritional, Mineral

Introduction

Plants accommodate a large source of variety of phytochemicals for the treatment of many diseases. The primary as well as secondary metabolites produced by the plants have distinctive pharmacological action and therapeutic uses. Hence the plants or the products obtained from them have been used for treating health disorders or diseases²⁰. As vegetables and fruits come under perishable commodities, preserving them for longer time for their usage is essential. One of the best techniques to preserve these is Dehydration. In the dehydration process, different parameters and tools are involved to enhance the

nutritional profile and increase shelf life of food product. One such way of dehydration is through the process of osmosis and this method of dehydration through osmotic agents is known as Osmotic Dehydration. It is low-energy process that can be used to preserve high nutritional products due to low temperatures and lack of oxygen during the process. Osmotic dehydration is a process in which water content in the food product is reduced after pre-treating with the osmotic solutions².

Chayote (*Sechium edule* L.), is a seasonal vegetable crops belongs to gourd family *Cucurbitaceae* cultivated in tropical and subtropical region. It is a tender perennial vine type plant that produces a pear shaped, pale green to white, mild flavor and crispy textures having single seed, feasible in warm season for high productivity and growth. Currently there are ten species accepted to exist, eight of which are wild (*S. Chinantlense*, *S.compositum*, *S. hintonii*, *S. talamancense*, *S. panamense*, *S. pittieri*, *S. venosum* and *S. vilosum*) and two cultivated (*S. tabaco* and *S. edule*)¹³. Chayote is known for high fiber, low lipid and calorie content, but it is vital source of minerals, amino acids and vitamins¹³. The researchers reported that the vegetable exhibited diuretic and anti-inflammatory properties. In India, chayote was called different vernacular names are squash (Assamese), quash (Bengali), chow-chow (Hindi), seemakattirikikai (Tamil), seemebadane (Kannada), respectively. The chayote has been gaining popularity for its multiple applications like cooked vegetables, fermented pickles, candy, juice, murabba, cakes and snake foods. Hence, consumer is preferred to chayote instead of other vegetables like potato, gourd, brinjal for its varied uses and potential health benefits¹⁰. Chayote edible parts contain a wide diversity of bioactive compounds, such as peroxidases, alkaloids, saponins, phenolic acids, flavonoids, carotenoids, cucurbitane triterpenoids and phytosterols⁴. Chayote has been reported to present antibacterial,¹⁴ antioxidant, antihypertensive⁹ and antiepileptic⁸ activities. Other potential applications of the different parts of chayote plant are the cosmetic, pharmaceutical and nanomaterial industries, as well as its use in biotechnological processes. Chayote fields are routinely cleared for replanting; this practice produces large amounts of root which are destroyed despite its potentially high commercial value. Also, fruits that are not in accordance with market classification standard are wasted¹⁶. Apart from its nutritional value, different parts of the plant have also been used in traditional medicine for the treatment of renal diseases and other illnesses such as diabetes, obesity, arteriosclerosis, among others⁵. As in many instances, these health effects have been linked to a high antioxidant activity; in fact, these benefits are a consequence of the bioactive composition present in each part of the plant^{11,6}.

Materials & Method

1. **Procurement of Raw material:** Fresh Chayote was procured from local market, Faridabad, Haryana. Other materials that were used in the study (Coriander, Mint leaves, Oranges) were procured from Banasthali Vidyapith. All chemicals and reagents utilized in this study were of analytical grade (AR).

2. **Sample preparation:** 1 kg of fresh chayote vegetable was weighed and was washed and cleaned with distilled water 3 to 4 times to remove dirt, contaminants and extraneous materials including damaged parts. Then, they were chopped evenly for further processing. They were then stored in proper storage conditions for further use.
3. **Design of the experiment:** The pre-processed vegetable samples were divided in 4 different proportions and are described in Table 1.

Table 1: Description of processing of chayote vegetable sample

Sample code	Description of the processing treatment
FV (S1)	Control (fresh sample with no treatment)
OD1 (S2)	50° brix for immersion time 60 mins with hot air drying for 6 hrs at 40°C
OD2 (S3)	40° brix for immersion time 80 mins with hot air drying for 6 hrs at 40°C
OD3 (S4)	70° brix for immersion time 90 mins with hot air drying for 6 hrs at 40°C

4. **Osmotic Dehydration of vegetable samples:** The osmotic solutions were prepared by dissolving appropriate amounts of osmotic agent including Sucrose and NaCl in 1:1 ratio in distilled water.

After the treatment, the samples were removed from the solution and were rinsed with distilled water. The treated samples were spread evenly on stainless steel tray and these were placed in hot air oven at pre-set conditions. Subsequently, these samples were packed on air tight zip lock polyethylene bags and were stored at room temperature for further usage.

5. **Determination of Proximate Composition:** The proximate analysis was done for Moisture, Ash, Protein, Fat and Fibre by standard methods¹ and carbohydrate was calculated by difference method.
6. **Determination of Mineral Content:** The minerals analysis was done for- Iron, Calcium, Potassium, Sodium and Phosphorous were estimated by Atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS) method (AOAC, 2023). Concisely, 0.5 g of vegetable sample powder was accurately taken and transferred into Teflon digestion tubes. To each tube, 5 mL of nitric acid was added, and the mixture was vortexed for 30 s. The tubes were then placed in a preheated microwave digester and subjected to digestion at 120°C for 5 min. After digestion, the tubes were cooled to room temperature and diluted with 50 mL of distilled water.
7. **Development of Juices:** Juices were developed by incorporating chayote, herbal extract and orange juice in different proportions which are described in Table 2.

Table 2: Composition of Juices from Chayote Vegetable

Product Code	Orange Juice (ml)	Herbal Extract* (ml)	Chayote Juice (ml)
B1	15	25	60
B2	15	20	65
B3	15	15	70
B4	15	10	75

*Herbal Extract = Black and White salt (1:1) + Corriander leaves, Mint leaves and Citric Acid (1:1:1)

Sensory Evaluation: Sensory evaluation of formulated juices was performed by using 9- point hedonic scale (ranging from like extremely to dislike extremely)²². The sensory attributes for juices evaluation included Aroma, Color, Taste, Texture, Appearance, Aftertaste and Overall Acceptability. The evaluation was carried out by 30 semi-trained panel members who were from Food Science and Nutrition department and were aged between 20- 30 years.

Statistical Analysis: The IBM SPSS Statistics software (version 20) was used to statistically interpret the data. The triplicate determinations of Mean \pm Standard Deviation (SD), One- Way ANOVA, Least Significance Difference (LSD) were used to express the results of the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Proximate composition: Table 3 shows the proximate composition of Fresh and Osmotic dehydrated Chayote samples.

Table 3: Proximate composition of Fresh and Osmotic Dehydrated Chayote vegetable samples

Nutrients (gm/100gm)	FV	OD1	OD2	OD3	F -value
Moisture	67.2 \pm 0.77 ^{bcd}	39.7 \pm 0.33 ^{acd} (60.3% \downarrow)	35.8 \pm 0.12 ^{ab} (64.2% \downarrow)	36.4 \pm 0.16 ^{ab} (63.6% \downarrow)	2430.20
Protein	1.2 \pm 0.08 ^{cd}	1.16 \pm 0.04 ^{cd} (98.84% \downarrow)	2.36 \pm 0.04 ^{abd} (97.64% \uparrow)	5.52 \pm 0.27 ^{abc} (94.48% \uparrow)	201.69

Fat	0.42 ± 0.06 [*]	0.3 ± 0.1 ^c (99.7% ↓)	0.6 ± 0.2 ^c (99.4% ↑)	0.8 ± 0.1 [*] (99.2% ↑)	2.05
Fibre	1.38 ± 0.02 ^{bcd}	9.36 ± 0.18 ^{acd} (90.64% ↑)	8.81 ± 0.06 ^{abd} (91.19% ↑)	5.21 ± 0.02 ^{abc} (94.79% ↑)	4699.77
Ash	7.73 ± 0.17 ^{bcd}	2.63 ± 0.2 ^{acd} (97.37% ↓)	3.73 ± 0.17 ^{abd} (96.27% ↓)	4.43 ± 0.25 ^{abc} (95.57% ↓)	237.69
Carbohydrate	11.7 ± 0.17 ^{bcd}	57.3 ± 0.08 ^{acd} (42.7% ↑)	52.7 ± 0.05 ^{abd} (47.3% ↑)	55.7 ± 0.17 ^{abc} (44.3% ↑)	384.34

Each data is the mean ± SD of three replicates. F- Values are significant at $P \leq 0.001$. Different letters (a-d) at different columns of each parameter denote significant difference between means ($p \leq 0.05$). *FV- Fresh Vegetable sample/ Control, OD1- Osmotic Dehydrated Vegetable sample 1, OD2- Osmotic Dehydrated Vegetable sample 2, OD3- Osmotic Dehydrated Vegetable sample 3

Moisture: The results indicated that moisture content (g/100g) of the samples differed significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) across the samples. Osmotic dehydration resulted in significant decrease (35.8 ± 0.12) in moisture content as compared to control (67.2 ± 0.77). Results of moisture content ranged from (67.2 ± 0.77 to 35.8 ± 0.12), which is highest in control sample and lowest in OD2 sample. The results were slightly lower to the findings in study that stated the moisture content to be 93.9 ± 0.8 (g/100g) in pulp and 35 ± 3.01 (g/100g) in peel of chayote vegetable⁷. Another researcher reported the moisture content to be 93.27 ± 0.16 (%) in fresh chayote and 63.58 ± 0.26 (%) in osmo-dehydrated chayote vegetable which was found to have significant difference from the findings of present study¹⁰. This might be due to use of different parameters (osmotic agents, solution ratio, time and temperature).

Protein: The results indicated that protein content (g/100g) of the samples differed significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) across the samples. Osmotic dehydration resulted in significant increase (5.52 ± 0.27) in the protein content as compared to control (1.2 ± 0.08). Results of protein content ranged from (1.16 ± 0.04 to 5.52 ± 0.27), which is highest in OD3 sample and lowest in OD1 sample. The results were in accordance to the findings of study that stated protein content in fresh chayote plant shoots ranging from 3.01 to 3.33 (%)¹⁵. Another researcher reported protein content to be in range from 0.9 to 1.1 (%) in chayote pulp and 3 (g/100g) in chayote leaf which was found to be supporting the findings of the present study¹².

Fat: The results indicated that fat content (g/100g) of the samples differed significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) across the samples. Osmotic dehydration resulted in significant increase (0.8 ± 0.1) in the fat content as compared to control (0.42 ± 0.06). Results of fat content ranged from (0.3 ± 0.1 to 0.8 ± 0.1), which is

highest in OD3 sample and lowest in OD1 sample. The results were in accordance to the findings of study that stated fat content in chayote vegetable to be 0.13 (g/100g)¹⁸. Another researcher reported fat content in chayote plant shoots to be ranging from 0.14 to 0.21 (%) which was found to be supporting the findings of present study¹⁵.

Fibre: The results indicated that fibre content (g/100g) of the samples differed significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) across the samples. Osmotic dehydration resulted in significant increase (9.36 ± 0.18) in the fibre content as compared to control (1.38 ± 0.02). Results of fibre content ranged from (1.38 ± 0.02 to 9.36 ± 0.18), which is highest in OD1 sample and lowest in control sample. The results were in accordance to the findings of study that stated fibre content ranging from 1.35 to 2.04 (%) in chayote vegetable¹⁵. Another researcher reported fibre content as 1.1 (g/100g) in chayote leafs and 0.4 to 1.0 (%) in pulp of chayote vegetable which was found to be supporting the findings of the present study¹².

Ash: The results indicated that ash content (g/100g) of the samples differed significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) across the samples. Osmotic dehydration resulted in significant decrease (2.63 ± 0.2) in ash content as compared to control (7.73 ± 0.17). Results of ash content ranged from (2.63 ± 0.2 to 7.73 ± 0.17), which is highest in control sample and lowest in OD1 sample. The results were in accordance to the findings of study that stated ash content to be 6.03 ± 0.9 (g/100g) in pulp and 7.59 ± 1.09 (g/100g) in peel of chayote vegetable⁷. Another researcher reported the ash content to be 0.3 ± 0.4 (%) in fresh chayote and 0.45 ± 0.2 (%) in osmo-dehydrated chayote vegetable which was found to have significant difference from the findings of present study¹⁰. This might be due to use of different parameters (osmotic agents, solution ratio, time and temperature).

Carbohydrate: The results indicated that carbohydrate content (g/100g) of the samples differed significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) across the samples. Osmotic dehydration resulted in significant increase (57.3 ± 0.08) in carbohydrate content as compared to control (11.7 ± 0.17). Results of carbohydrate content ranged from (11.7 ± 0.17 to 57.3 ± 0.08), which is highest in OD1 sample and lowest in control sample. The results were in accordance to the findings of study that stated carbohydrate content in chayote shoot to be 36.6 (g/100g)¹². Another researcher reported the ash content as 4.42 (%) in fresh chayote and 3.66 (%) in osmo dehydrated chayote vegetable which had significant difference to the findings of the present study¹⁰. This might be due to use of different parameters (osmotic agents, solution ratio, time and temperature).

Figure 1: Proximate content of Fresh and Osmotic Dehydrated Chayote vegetable

2. Mineral content: Table 4 shows the mineral analysis of fresh and osmotic dehydrated Chayote vegetable samples

Table 4: Mineral content Analysis of Fresh and Osmotic Dehydrated chayote vegetable samples

Minerals (mg/100gm)	FV	OD1	OD2	OD3	F value
Iron	2.29 ± 0.14 ^c	2.13 ± 0.04 ^c (97.87% ↓)	1.88 ± 0.01 ^{abd} (98.12% ↓)	2.28 ± 0.01 ^c (97.72% ↓)	12.59
Calcium	3.22 ± 0.08 ^{bcd}	5.74 ± 0.13 ^{acd} (94.26% ↑)	4.6 ± 0.08 ^{abd} (95.4% ↑)	6.4 ± 0.27 ^{abc} (93.6% ↑)	153.01
Potassium	7.66 ± 0.27 ^{bcd}	9.69 ± 0.2 ^{acd} (90.31% ↑)	8.63 ± 0.12 ^{abd} (91.37% ↑)	10.21 ± 0.1 ^{abc} (89.79% ↑)	71.36
Sodium	24.66 ± 1.24 ^{bcd}	72.0 ± 0.81 ^{acd} (28% ↑)	57.66 ± 0.47 ^{abd} (42.34% ↑)	86.3 ± 1.24 ^{abc} (13.7% ↑)	1394.14
Phosphorous	2.42 ± 0.1 ^{bcd}	4.67 ± 0.12 ^{acd} (95.33% ↑)	3.81 ± 0.08 ^{abd} (96.19% ↑)	5.58 ± 0.27 ^{abc} (94.42% ↑)	130.51

Iodine	4.23 ± 0.04 ^{bcd}	6.3 ± 0.16 ^{acd} (93.7% ↑)	5.25 ± 0.1 ^{abd} (94.75% ↑)	7.46 ± 0.17 ^{abc} (92.54% ↑)	221.38
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Each data is the mean ± SD of three replicates. F- Values are significant at $P \leq 0.001$. Different letters (a-d) at different columns of each parameter denote significant difference between means ($p \leq 0.05$). *FV- Fresh Vegetable sample/ Control, OD1- Osmotic Dehydrated Vegetable sample 1, OD2- Osmotic Dehydrated Vegetable sample 2, OD3- Osmotic Dehydrated Vegetable sample 3

Iron: The results indicated that iron content (mg/100g) of the samples differed significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) across the samples. Osmotic dehydration resulted in slight decrease (1.88 ± 0.01) in iron content as compared to control (2.29 ± 0.14). Results of iron content ranged from (1.88 ± 0.01 to 2.29 ± 0.14), which is highest in control sample and lowest in OD2 sample. The results were in accordance to the findings of study that stated iron content in chayote leaves and fruit to be 1-2 (mg/100g) and 0.33 (mg/100g) respectively¹². Another researcher reported iron content in chayote to be 0.34 (mg/100g) which were found to be slightly lower to the findings of the present study¹⁸.

Calcium: The results indicated that calcium content (mg/100g) of the samples differed significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) across the samples. Osmotic dehydration resulted in significant increase (6.4 ± 0.27) in calcium content as compared to control (3.22 ± 0.08). Results of calcium content ranged from (3.22 ± 0.08 to 6.4 ± 0.27), which is highest in OD3 sample and lowest in control sample. The results were in accordance to the findings of study that stated calcium content in chayote roots to be 7 (mg/100g)²¹. Another researcher reported calcium content to be 17 (mg/100g) in chayote vegetable which was quite higher as compared to the findings of the present study¹⁸.

Potassium: The results indicated that potassium content (mg/100g) of the samples differed significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) across the samples. Osmotic dehydration resulted in significant increase (10.21 ± 0.1) in potassium content as compared to control (7.66 ± 0.27). Results of potassium content ranged from (7.66 ± 0.27 to 10.21 ± 0.1), which is highest in OD3 sample and lowest in control sample. The results of present study were quite higher to the findings of study that stated potassium content as 0.54 ± 0.03 (%) in fresh chayote vegetable³. Another researcher reported potassium content as (125 mg/100g) which had significant difference from the findings of the present study²¹.

Sodium: The results indicated that sodium content (mg/100g) of the samples differed significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) across the samples. Osmotic dehydration resulted in significant increase (86.3 ± 1.24) in sodium content as compared to control (24.66 ± 1.24). Results of sodium content ranged from (24.66 ± 1.24 to 86.3 ± 1.24), which is highest in OD3 sample and lowest in control sample. The results of the present study were remarkably higher as compared to the findings of study stated that sodium content as 2-5

(mg/100g) in fresh chayote vegetable¹⁸. Another researcher reported similar results to previous quoted research which stated sodium content as 2 (mg/100g) in chayote vegetable²¹.

Phosphorous: The results indicated that phosphorous content (mg/100g) of the samples differed significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) across the samples. Osmotic dehydration resulted in significant increase (5.58 ± 0.27) in phosphorous content as compared to control (2.42 ± 0.1). Results of phosphorous content ranged from (2.42 ± 0.1 to 5.58 ± 0.27), which is highest in OD3 sample and lowest in control sample. The results of the present study were slightly higher as compared to the findings of study that stated phosphorous content found to be (0.2 ± 0.006) in chayote vegetable³. Another researcher reported phosphorous content in chayote vegetable as 36 (mg/100g) which had significant difference from the findings of the present study¹².

Iodine: The results indicated that iodine content (mg/100g) of the samples differed significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) across the samples. Osmotic dehydration resulted in significant increase (7.46 ± 0.17) in iodine content as compared to control (4.23 ± 0.04). Results of iodine content ranged from (4.23 ± 0.04 to 7.46 ± 0.17), which is highest in OD3 sample and lowest in control sample. The results were in accordance to the findings of study that stated iodine content to be ranged from (5-6 mg/kg)¹⁷. Another report concluded iodine content in chayote vegetable ranged from (0.5-7.5 mcg)¹⁹.

Figure 2: Mineral Analysis of Fresh and Osmotic Dehydrated Chayote vegetable

Sensory Evaluation: Sensory evaluation serves as an essential factor in understanding customer's feasible options and imbibing preferences. The sensory evaluation was done for developed juices which were made at different concentrations with a blend of Chayote juice, Orange Juice, and Herbal extract. A 9-Point hedonic scale was used by the panel members for the evaluation under controlled conditions.

Juice was freshly prepared prior to the evaluation procedure with the help of electronic juicer grinder in cooking lab of Banasthali Vidyapith, Rajasthan. All the ingredients were cleaned and washed with distilled water 3 to 4 times to remove all dirt and dust particles to maintain hygiene and sanitation. Then, Sensory evaluation of Juices was done and each panel member was prior informed and consent was taken into consideration. Out of the juice with different concentrations, B2 was the most acceptable having composition as { 100 ml Juice = 65 ml Chayote juice + 20 ml Orange juice + 15 ml Herbal Extract }.

Table 5: Sensory evaluation of juices developed from Chayote vegetable

Sample	Color	Appearance	Flavour	Consistency	Taste	Mouth Feel	Aftertaste	Overall Acceptability
Standard	8.6±0.7	8.5±0.6	8.4±0.6	8.1±0.9	8.3±0.7	8.3±0.7	8.1±0.8	8.4±0.6
B1	8±0.9**	7.7±0.7**	7.5±0.8**	7.7±0.8**	7.8±0.8**	7.7±0.7**	7.4±0.7**	7.6±0.6**
B2	7.8±0.8**	8±0.6**	7.8±1.0**	7.7±0.7**	8±1.1**	7.8±0.6**	7.8±1.2**	8±1.0**
B3	8±0.8**	7.7±1.1*	7.2±1.3*	7.4±1.3**	7.3±1.5*	7.4±1.3**	7.1±1.7*	7.3±1.2*
B4	8±0.9**	7.4±1.0*	7.2±1.4*	7.3±1.4*	7.1±1.5*	7.2±1.2**	7±1.7**	7.3±1.2*

* - denotes significant difference and ** – denotes non- significant difference at different columns of each parameter denote significant difference between means (p ≤0.05)

Figure 3: Sensory evaluation of juices developed from Chayote vegetable

CONCLUSION

The findings from the present study revealed that Osmotic Dehydration resulted in significant loss ($p \leq 0.05$) in moisture content which signifies its longer shelf life as compared to the fresh chayote. Proximate and mineral composition showed a significant increase ($p \leq 0.05$) in treated samples of the vegetable. Thus, preservation using osmotic agents (Sucrose and NaCl) can be a possible alternative to utilize underutilized vegetable in formulation of functional beverages. Mineral analysis showed that calcium, potassium, sodium, phosphorous and iodine significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) increased after the application of osmotic dehydration technique. Sensory Evaluation of the developed juices was carried out using 9-point hedonic rating scale. The results of the evaluation showed that Sample 2 (B2) scored highest as compared to other formulations. There was observed no significant difference in the most acceptable sample as compared to standard. The results derived from osmotic dehydrated chayote samples that were given treatment at set conditions showed that it is the promising alternative to the conventional drying technique. As it economical, time saving, it can be a better choice in the food preservation and processing industry.

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It's not applicable.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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